

A Learner Needs Analysis Report

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Abstract

The following Needs Analysis Report is dedicated to Curriculum Development in Second Language Acquisition. As the main objectives of this small-scale research are to analyze and identify learners' needs in terms of language learning and help instructors to create more effective courses in terms of second language acquisition. Regarding needs analysis report, several types of research methods are implemented in this research in order to get results that are more reliable.

Keywords: Questionnaire, Curriculum development, Needs analysis report, syllabus,

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Introduction

One of the most important component of curriculum development is considered needs analysis. As Richards (2001) defined “need analysis” as a process of collecting information about learner’s needs. Additionally, Graves (2000) stated that the aim of needs analysis is to find out what learners know or what they are able to do and what they need to learn or should do. Need analysis can be described as a core element of curriculum development, which involves looking for and elucidate information needs at the end of the course. Needs analysis is consisting of several stages which analyze and find out answers to the questions that identify learner’s needs.

In order to complete *Needs Analysis Report*, I went to the Uzbekistan State World Languages University and observed several classes there. During the observations, I looked through the syllabus and the curriculum of that university. According to the researches, most of subjects at the university have been organized to shift the students from B1 level to C1 level according to Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) standard for a four-year academic period. During the research, I mainly observed reading, writing, listening, and speaking classes, which last five or six semesters during four academic years. In addition, we should consider that the lessons usually continue 80 minutes and teachers try to prepare and utilize their lesson plans according to the curriculum, which is confirmed by the government. After observing several classes, I chose one male student because I noticed that he has a lack of English in reading, which is needed to improve. That’s why, I chose him and he is a third year student of third English language faculty. Participant is 23 years old. He and his group mates are fifteen students in the group, two of them are boys, and others are girls. He and his group mates are studying for bachelor’s degree in Foreign language and literature (English language) classes. Moreover, he mentioned that he began to learn English language when he was 15 years old and nowadays his English language proficiency level is intermediate. According to observations, the participant demonstrated good speaking skills during lessons and he mentioned that he prepares his writing tasks considering every detail of each task. However, I admitted that he has a lack of vocabulary building that’s why reading is always complicated skill for him. Therefore, I saw that the teacher and students created positive atmosphere in class, which is very crucial for reaching success in studying. Furthermore, one of the most important thing that I care while doing a research is considering agreement of learner to participate in the survey that is why I explain the learner about what kind of information would be taken from him and what he have to do. I warned him that his personal information could be given in the research and he is supposed to sign a consent form before beginning the survey.

Methods

There are several types of procedures, which is useful in collecting needs analysis report. As Richards (2001) stated that procedures, which you utilize in your research are usually associated with the kind of information that you are analyzing. In addition, he advised that it could be beneficial that utilizing two or more types of procedures in the survey, because using single procedure can lead to inaccurate and partial results. According to Richards (2001), the following types of procedures are popular with their common usage:

Table 1

1	Questionnaires	it is considered the most common one among other instruments
2	Self-rating	it can be utilized to analyze learner’s knowledge and abilities
3	Observation	it can be useful for analyzing and evaluating behavior of learner
4	Meeting	it can be helpful for collecting much information on a single

		issue.
5	Interviews	it usually explore needs of learner in detail.
6	Collecting learner language samples	it can be collected by written or oral tasks and achievement or performance tests.
7	Case studies	it can be useful to collect data from a group of people
8	Task analysis	it is analysis of kind of tasks, which learner would act in different educational settings.

After looking through advantages and disadvantages of each procedure, I decided to utilize four instruments to take result that is more accurate in my small-scale research. Firstly, I want to take an interview from the participant in order to collect vital information about personality traits, goals, and interests of the learner. That's why I made a list of questions, which investigates learner's goals, learning style and strategies, and personality. Additionally, one of beneficial side of interview is that researcher can identify accurate issues in the process of face-to-face interview. Secondly, I utilize questionnaire which consists of 6 items that identify learner's difficulties and weaknesses of learner in learning process. Questionnaire is adapted from Marshall (2002) and it is outlined to find out needs of intermediate and advanced level learner. One of the advantages of questionnaire is that it would give a chance to learners to analyze and evaluate their weaknesses. Additionally, I wanted to correlate the questionnaire with self-rating test which consists of 20 items and the procedure is helpful to clarify weaknesses in-depth during the research. Moreover, self-rating is considered as one of effective instrument to determine learner's abilities and knowledge based on four skills. Finally, the most important tool which is utilized in this research is a sample of learner's writing because a piece of learner's writing work can clarify accurate needs of the learner. Therefore, I prepared a task in which learner have to write a letter that consists of 150 words and it should be informal letter.

Results

Results of Need Analysis Report would be discussed in this part of research. Firstly, I took interview by asking five questions. According to answers of the learner, it is clear thing that the main aim of the learner is to be English for Specific Purpose (ESP) teacher and to conduct lessons at the university. In addition, he stated that his learning style is visual and he usually like to learn things by watching and memorizing thing. However, he also mentioned that he is auditory learner partially, which means he is able to learn things by listening and discussing problems. In addition, he stated that he usually use some strategies like scanning and skimming in reading tasks. However, he added that he had difficulty in reading because of a lack of vocabulary building. When it comes to his personality, the first thing that he like is hard working and taking risks. Furthermore, after graduating university, he is going to be a teacher and he realized that his future career has a big responsibility. According to interview, it is clear thing that the learner has difficulties in reading and vocabulary.

In addition, in order to evaluate learner's knowledge and ability, I utilized 6-item questionnaire and 20-item self-rating test. According to results of questionnaire, participant stated that he had some troubles in vocabulary building as he cannot remember words while he listens, but he is able to do so when he sees in the context. Moreover, he stated that he wants to improve his writing and reading skill and one of the most difficult for him is vocabulary. In order to take accurate results of learner's needs, I prepared self-rating and correlated with questionnaire. As it is mentioned above that self-rating test consists of 20-item questions. According to *Table 2*, the learner has lowest rate in reading skills (average 1.8) which learner need to improve his reading skills. It can happen because of a lack of vocabulary.

Table 2- Self-rating test results

Skills	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	Average	
Reading		2					2	1	2					2								1.8
Writing															2	2	3	3	3			2.6
Listening										2	2	2	2							2		2
Speaking	2		2	2	2	2																2

Always – 3 point Sometimes – 2 point Never – 1 point

The last tool which I have utilized in this research is a sample of learner's writing. The results show that learner has good writing skills and the letter is well organized with no considering minor errors. The learner tried to use proper grammar and vocabulary, but it is some minor mistakes, which show usage of inappropriate vocabulary in some parts of work. However, the letter had a good look with many structures as the participant utilized a variety of subordinating conjunctions. Accordingly, it is well-organized work by taking into account the meaning, structure, grammar and partially vocabulary.

Discussion

After analyzing needs of learner by utilizing different procedures, it became clear that the participant has a good productive skill in English language. Moreover, the participant is not only visual learner but also he has improved his listening skills. Although the participant utilized some reading strategies in learning process, he has some problems with his reading skills because of a lack of vocabulary building. Correlation of all used procedures shows that learner's urgent needs is to improve both reading skills and vocabulary building. According to my viewpoint, these problems can be solved by practicing and learning words daily. If I conducted this group or student, I would have taught vocabulary in context because by this way learners can spontaneously recall words and reading for meaning can also be effective for improving vocabulary knowledge. In addition, it is advisable that a teacher should utilize appropriate materials according to learner level and needs considering syllabus and curriculum requirement.

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